

SiDMACIB plugin- modelling phase: Manual (2018)

1. Installing SiDMACIB plugin for grasshopper

Grasshopper Assembly File "Sidmacib.gha" should be saved in the folder shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Installing the plugin

2. Modelling Process

The assemblage is modelled in two phases (Figure 2). In the first phase, the overall surface of the assemblage is designed. In the second phase, interfaces of each block is modelled.

Figure 2. Pipeline: 1) surface modelling: using a set of primary shapes, the outer interface of the assemblage is modelled; 2) the outer surface is discretized; 3) specifying the assemblage thickness, the inner surface is offset; 4) outer interfaces of blocks are modelled; 5) specifying the orientation of a planar interface, its validity is checked; 6) inner interfaces of blocks are modelled; 7) interlocking interfaces of blocks are modelled

2.1. Surface Modelling

2.1.1. Outer surface Modelling

Using seven primary shapes, the outer surface can be modelled.

Component	Description
Circular Arch component (CArch)	
Input	
Base Point (BPt)	Mid-point of arch base line
Extrusion Direction (ED)	the direction of the arch extrusion
Radius (R)	Radius of arch
Height (H)	Distance between apex and base point of arch

Output

Circular Arch (CA)

The screenshot displays the 'Circular Arch (CA)' component within a CAD software interface. The component is represented as a node in a node-based environment, with inputs for Base Point (BPt), Extrusion Direction (ED), Radius (R), Height (H), and Distance (D). The component is connected to a 'Vec' node, which is used to define the extrusion direction. The 3D view shows a red circular arch on a grid, with a red dot indicating the base point and a green line representing the extrusion direction. The interface also shows a toolbar with various modeling tools and a zoom level of 176%.

Component	Description
Freeform Shell (FSh)	Construct a freeform shell by a set of curves

Input

Curves (Cs)	Curves on shell
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Output

Freeform Shell (FS)

Component	Description
Oval Arch (OArch)	

Input

Base Point (BPt)	Mid point of arch base line
Extrusion Direction (ED)	The direction of the arch extrusion
Horizontal Radius (HR)	Horizontal radius of arch
Vertical Radius (VR)	Vertical radius of arch
Height (H)	Distance between apex and base point of arch
Depth (D)	Depth of arch

Output

Oval Arch (OA)

Component	Description
Pointed Arch (PArch)	
Input	
Base Point (BPt)	Mid point of arch base line
Extrusion Direction (ED)	The direction of the arch extrusion
Radius (R)	Radius of arch
Depth (D)	Depth of arch
Smoothness (S)	A value determining smoothness of curve

Output

Pointed Arch (PA)

Component	Description
Sail Linear Vault (SLVault)	
Input	
Base Point (BPt)	Mid point of vault base plane
Mid Height (MH)	Distance between apex and base point of vault
X Arch Height (XAH)	Distance between apex and base point of the arch in x direction
Y Arch Height (YAH)	Distance between apex and base point of the arch in y direction
X Arch Span (XAS)	Span of the arch in x direction
Y Arch Span (YAS)	Span of the arch in y direction
Smoothness (S)	A value determining smoothness of vault

Output

Sail Linear Vault (SLV)

Component

Description

Sail Radial Vault (SRVault)

Input

Base Point (BPt)	Mid point of vault base plane
Mid Height (MH)	Distance between apex and base point of vault
X Arch Height (XAH)	Distance between apex and base point of the arch in x direction
Y Arch Height (YAH)	Distance between apex and base point of the arch in y direction
X Arch Span (XAS)	Span of the arch in x direction
Y Arch Span (YAS)	Span of the arch in y direction
Smoothness (S)	A value determining smoothness of vault

Output

Sail Radial Vault (SRV)

Component	Description
Spherical Dome (SphDome)	
Input	
Base Point (BPt)	Mid point of dome base plane
Radius (R)	Radius of dome
Height (H)	Distance between apex and base point of dome
Output	

Spherical Dome (SpD)

2.1.2. Outer surface Discretization

Using Divide Surface component, an assemblage can be discretized using stuck bonding pattern. U and V determine numbers of segments in U and V directions (Figure 3). The output is a data tree of points representing the corners of outer interfaces (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Discretizing the outer surface using Divide Surface component.

Figure 4. Data tree for outputs of Divide Surface component.

2.2. Interface Modelling

Each block is cuboid, including an outer, an inner, and four interlocking interfaces. All block edges are straight segments and the interlocking interfaces must be planar. In the following the inputs and outputs of components are represented. The components are under construction and are presented for comprehensive introduction of the modelling process.

Component	Description
Outer Interface (OI)	
Input	
Nodes on Discretized Outer Surface (NOS)	
Output	
Outer Interface Corners (OIC)	
Outer Interface Segments (OIS)	
Outer Interface Faces (OIF)	
Outer Graph Nodes (OGN)	
Outer Graph Edges (OGE)	

The outputs are data trees of the corners, segments, and faces of outer interfaces (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Data tree for outputs of Outer Interface component.

Component	Description
Interlocking plane (IIP)	
Input	
Outer Interface Segments (OIS)	
Outer Graph Nodes (OGN)	
Interlocking Plane Index (IPI)	Index of an interlocking plane which its orientation needs adjustment
Interlocking Plane Orientation (IPO)	angle of an interlocking plane which its orientation needs adjustment
Output	
Interlocking Plane Lines (IPL)	

Component

Description

Inner Interface (InI)

Input

Interlocking Plane Lines (IPL)

Lines at intersection of interlocking planes

Output

Inner Interface Corners (InIC)

Inner Interface Segments (InIS)

Inner Interface Faces (InIF)

Component

Description

Interlocking Interface (III)

Input

Outer Interface Segments (OIS)

Inner Interface Segments (InIS)

Output

Interlocking Interface Corners (IIIC)

Interlocking Interface Segments (IIIS)

Interlocking Interface Faces (IIIF)

